

PSYCHOLOGICAL PROFILE OF ADOLESCENTS WITH DIFFERENT LEVELS OF CONFLICTOLOGICAL CULTURE DEVELOPMENT*

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Abstract

The psychological development of adolescents is shaped by the dual nature of their position, their internal contradictions and emotional instability. Due to a lack of self-regulation skills, excessive impulsivity and a fear of rejection, adolescents often perceive emerging conflicts as a direct threat to their self-esteem. Combined with the spontaneity of interaction within various peer groups, this significantly increases the likelihood of conflictual behaviour and the risk of resorting to destructive strategies — aggression, avoidance of the problem, or suppression of one's own needs. In this regard, the development of a conflict resolution culture in late adolescence takes on particular relevance and importance. This article presents an analysis of the psychological profiles of older adolescents depending on their level of development of a conflict-resolution culture. The study identifies qualitative differences in attitudes towards oneself and others, the level of personal conflict, and the behavioural strategies chosen in conflict situations. The results show that the level of conflict management culture acts as an important regulator of interpersonal interaction, emotional stability and self-esteem in adolescence.

Key words: Psychological profile, Conflictological culture of personality, Adolescents, Self-attitude, Behavioral styles, Conflictiness.

1. Introduction

Adolescence is a crucial and sensitive period characterised by the intensive development of identity, a reassessment of values, and the formation of new models of interpersonal communication (Ilyin, 2009). During this time, the social sphere of an adolescent's interactions expands and deepens significantly, and communication becomes a priority and a central activity (Bodalev, 2015). However, the specific

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nature of this age is inextricably linked to a multitude of challenges. The process of psychological development during adolescence is largely determined by the ambivalence of the adolescent's personal stance (Vygotsky, 2021), marked by internal contradictions and pronounced emotional lability. Due to a lack of developed self-regulation mechanisms, heightened impulsivity and an acute fear of social rejection, adolescents tend to interpret interpersonal conflicts as a direct threat to the stability of their self-esteem and the integrity of their 'self-image'.

This psychological vulnerability, combined with the spontaneous nature of communication within peer reference groups, significantly destabilises social interaction (Van Kleef & Cote, 2022). This not only increases the overall frequency of conflict situations but also heightens the risk of employing destructive behavioural strategies. These include overt aggression as a means of defending ego status, escapism (avoiding problem-solving) or the maladaptive suppression of one's own significant needs, which in the long term may lead to increased neuroticism and socialisation disorders. This necessity can be justified by the following key factors:

- Prevention of destructive behaviour. The development of a conflict resolution culture helps adolescents develop skills for constructive interaction and the peaceful resolution of disputes (Gelfand et al., 2014). Adolescents learn to understand the true causes of conflicts, express their own position without aggression, and sincerely respect their opponent's point of view.

- Successful socialisation and adaptation. A culture of conflict resolution is inextricably linked to the development of empathy, tolerance, responsibility and emotional and volitional self-regulation, which are fundamental qualities for the integration of the individual into modern society (Kolominsky, 2003).

- Enhancing psychological well-being. Mastering the skills of healthy behaviour in conflicts reduces internal tension, protects the adolescent's personal boundaries and contributes to strengthening their overall psychological well-being (Bozhovich, 2009).

- Stimulating personal growth. With a sufficient level of development in conflict management culture, conflict ceases to be a destructive factor and becomes a source of growth, self-awareness and social development. The adolescent begins to view conflict in the context of positive change and the possibility of reconciling positions (Shcherbakova, 2011).

2. The theoretical framework

Interaction in conflict depends on a multitude of factors; in particular, the behavioural strategies employed become crucial. The way an individual interacts in conflict is invariably linked to how they relate to other people, the nature of their interpersonal relationships, and their attitude towards their opponents. This takes place within a specific system of social relations.

The theoretical foundations for the study of interpersonal relationships in adolescence were laid by L.S. Vygotsky (Vygotsky, 2021), who incorporated the concept of meaning into the analysis of interpersonal relationships, emphasising that it is the process of mutual understanding that determines the quality of human

communication. In his view, meaning arises in the context of interaction and depends on the extent to which the participants in communication are able to interpret and share one another's experiences, intentions and meanings. The deeper this mutual understanding, the more productive and harmonious communication becomes.

E.P. Ilyin (Ilyin, 2009) and I.S. Kon (Kon, 2018) examine interpersonal relationships through the prism of the emotional reactions accompanying human interaction, emphasising that communication inevitably reflects the individual's inner psychological world. The emotional component of relationships, in their view, serves as the most important indicator of the depth and nature of the bond between people. In the process of interaction, complex and multifaceted bonds are formed, in which both social norms and roles, as well as individual experiences, attitudes and values, are manifested.

According to Y.L. Kolominsky (Kolominsky, 2003), D.I. Feldstein (Feldstein, 1996), the social world is, by its very nature, permeated by a system of relationships that form the basis of human existence. It is precisely through relationships that the life activity of the individual is revealed and realised in all its fullness, diversity of forms and content (Xiaodong, Guo-Ming, 2022). They determine the sphere of meaning and values of the individual, setting the direction of their development, behaviour and self-realisation.

The individual and their behaviour in conflict are determined not only by the system of relationships with the surrounding reality, but also with themselves. One of the primary forms of this relationship, which determines the individual's self-perception and self-development, is the relationship with oneself, or self-relationship. This term, and similar ones such as self-esteem, self-awareness, self-respect, self-acceptance, etc., began to be studied over a century and a half ago, and has its origins in the works of W. James (Leary, 1990).

Thus, the complexity and contradictions of adolescence not only provoke interpersonal conflicts but also provide an excellent, sensitive platform for the formation of a conflict-resolution culture.

The introduction of scientifically grounded practices for optimising behaviour in conflict is becoming a vital tool, enabling adolescents to safely navigate the crises of growing up and build mature, harmonious relationships with the world around them.

The focus of this study was therefore on the characteristics of conflict culture, conflict behaviour, strategies for dealing with conflict, and adolescents' attitudes towards themselves and others.

The aim of our study is to examine the characteristics of conflict culture and to develop a programme for fostering conflict culture among older adolescents.

We formulated the main **hypothesis** of the study: there are differences in the characteristics of attitudes towards oneself and others, conflict proneness, and behavioural strategies in conflict among older adolescents with varying levels of development of a conflict-resolution culture.

3. Methods and experimental group

To achieve the stated objective and carry out the tasks set, the following diagnostic methods were used:

The questionnaire 'Level of Development of an Individual's Conflict-Management Culture' by O.I. Shcherbakova. The method is based on polar characteristics and contains 12 pairs of statements reflecting various aspects of conflict-management culture (Shcherbakova, 2005). The statements presented in it relate to human behaviour, both in conflict situations and in connection with the resolution of problems arising in interpersonal interaction.

The 'Level of Personal Conflict' test (V.I. Andreev) identifies the general level of personal conflict and determines the subject's overall level of conflict, without differentiating the specific manifestations of their conflict behaviour according to strategies (Nepomnyaschaya, 2001).

The Thomas-Kilmann Test (Kenneth W. Thomas and Ralph H. Kilmann) identifies behavioural styles in conflict situations. It not only reveals a typical reaction to conflict but also explains how effective and appropriate it is, whilst providing information on alternative methods of resolving the conflict. According to K. Thomas and R. Kilmann, the typology of conflict behaviour is based on two behavioural styles: a person's attention to the interests of others involved in the conflict, and assertiveness, an emphasis on protecting one's own interests (Nepomnyaschaya, 2001).

T. Leary's methodology is used to study an individual's self-perception and their relationships within a small group. A small group refers to a family, a work team, an interest group, etc. Within small groups, two main relational factors are characteristic: dominance and friendliness. At the same time, a qualitative analysis is conducted to compare and contrast self-assessment, the ideal 'self', and the assessments of other members of the small group. From the test results obtained, conclusions can be drawn regarding the expression of the personality type and the degree to which an individual's behaviour is adapted to the group (Posokhova, Solovyova, 2008).

S.R. Pantelev's method for studying self-relations is designed to identify the structure of an individual's self-relations, as well as the intensity of individual components of self-relations: closedness, self-confidence, self-direction, reflected self-relations, self-worth, self-attachment, internal conflict and self-blame (Bodalev et al., 2000).

The data obtained were subjected to qualitative and quantitative analysis using methods of descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA and Pearson's correlation analysis. To construct profiles, the sample was divided into three subgroups: those with high, medium and low levels of development of conflict culture.

The sample consisted of 307 students aged 16–18 from grades 10–12 at the Tit Majoresc and Mihai Greuc secondary schools, residing in Chisinau, comprising 141 girls and 166 boys.

4. Discussion of results

Based on the empirical study conducted, psychological profiles of older adolescents were drawn up, which clearly demonstrate qualitative differences in their inner world, self-perception and social behaviour depending on the level of development of their conflict management culture. Figure 1 shows the profile of an adolescent with a high level of development of conflict management culture and Figure 2 shows the profile of a teenager with a low level of development of a conflict culture.

Figure 1. Profile of an adolescent with a high level of conflict management culture

Figure 2. Profile of an adolescent with a low level of conflict management culture

In terms of conflict levels and conflict behaviour styles, adolescents with a high level of conflict culture exhibit a low level of conflict (F=7.999), manifested in relationships, predominantly through cooperation (F=5.120), oriented towards constructive modes of interaction, whilst adolescents with a low level of conflict

culture exhibit a high level of conflict, expressed through a high degree of rivalry with others.

Adolescents with a high conflict culture are able to express their thoughts appropriately, listen, understand their partner's point of view, and avoid aggression and manipulation. They act appropriately in conflict, preferring constructive strategies (cooperation, seeking solutions) over aggression or withdrawal. Adolescents with a low conflict management culture display a high level of conflict, as they are less able to recognise and manage their emotions; they tend to react impulsively and struggle with empathy. This is exacerbated by a tendency towards black-and-white thinking, poor analysis of the consequences of conflict, and difficulty in finding compromise solutions. Such adolescents' communication is often aggressive or avoidant, and they struggle to understand other points of view. They tend to use destructive strategies more frequently (competition, withdrawal, aggression) and disregard social norms.

A low level of conflict management culture among adolescents is accompanied by high levels of internal conflict ($F=5.371$).

Adolescents with different levels of conflict culture differ significantly in terms of self-concept. Adolescents with a high level of conflict culture demonstrate a low level of self-blame ($F=4.834$).

Adolescents with a high level of conflict culture demonstrate moderate self-attachment ($F=8.034$). Furthermore, adolescents with a high conflict culture demonstrate a high level of reflected self-concept ($F=7.092$). Adolescents with a high conflict culture demonstrate a higher level of self-confidence ($F=11.857$). Attitudes towards others among adolescents with different levels of conflict culture are reflected in differences in aggressive ($F=7.816$) and authoritarian types of interpersonal relationships ($F=11.870$).

For the sake of clarity, we have summarised all significant differences and correlations in Table 1.

Table 1. Differences of characteristics of self-attitude, types of relationships towards others and style of behavior in conflict among adolescents with different levels of conflictological culture (ANOVA)

Source of Variation (between groups)	SS	MS	F-value	p-value
Conflictuality	190,530	95,265	7,999	0,00
Cooperation	72,241	36,121	5,120	0,07
Rivalry	13,193	6,597	1,675	0,189
Compromise	5,756	2,878	0,719	0,488
Avoidance	0,476	0,238	0,036	0,965
Adaptation	14,578	7,289	1,654	0,193
Closedness	4,363	2,181	1,820	0,164
Self-confidence	93,753	46,877	11,857	0,00

Self-leadership	9,797	4,899	1,483	0,229
Reflected self- concept	36,663	18,332	7,092	0,001
Self-worth	3,143	1,572	,370	0,691
Self-acceptance	70,267	35,134	13,098	0,00
Self-attachment	54,501	27,250	8,0.34	0,.00
Internal conflict	20,373	10,186	5,371	0,05
Self-blame	33,967	16,984	4,834	0,05
Aggressive style	121,640	60,820	7,816	0,00
Authoritarian style	299,259	149,629	11,870	0,00
Egoistic style	35,956	17,978	2,101	0,124
Suspicious style	39,819	19,910	2,092	0,125
Submissive style	21,552	10,776	,986	0,374
Dependent style	3,684	1,842	,262	0,769
Friendly style	11,126	5,563	,658	0,519
Altruistic style	28,696	14,348	1,484	0,228

The findings indicate that adolescents' level of conflict is significantly associated with all components of conflictological culture, including the culture of feelings, the culture of thinking, communicative culture, and behavioral culture. These correlations suggest a consistent pattern: higher levels of conflictological culture are linked to lower levels of conflict manifestation. Based on these results, it can be concluded that adolescents who demonstrate a well-developed conflictological culture exhibit more mature emotional and social functioning. Conversely, adolescents with lower levels of conflictological culture are more likely to become involved in conflict situations and tend to respond in less constructive and less adaptive ways.

Adolescents with a high level of conflictological culture display greater emotional awareness and competence. They are more capable of accurately recognizing both their own emotions and the emotions of others, which allows them to respond more appropriately in socially complex situations. Furthermore, they demonstrate the ability to regulate negative emotional states such as irritation, anger, and resentment. Their cognitive processing of conflict situations is also more advanced: they are able to analyze interpersonal dynamics constructively, consider multiple perspectives, anticipate consequences, and identify mutually acceptable solutions. Their thinking in conflict situations tends to be strategic rather than reactive, which enables them to pursue compromise and cooperation rather than escalation.

An important aspect of self-attitude in adolescents with a high level of conflictological culture is their reduced tendency toward self-blame, suggesting that more developed cognitive and behavioral competencies contribute to a more balanced and adaptive self-perception. Rather than engaging in excessive self-

criticism, these adolescents tend to reflect constructively on their own role in conflict situations. They are capable of recognizing personal responsibility without resorting to maladaptive patterns such as guilt or self-devaluation. The capacity for critical reflection plays a key role here: the more adolescents are inclined toward reflective thinking, the more effectively they are able to analyze conflict situations and adjust their behavior accordingly. In contrast, adolescents with a low level of conflictological culture tend to exhibit an external locus of responsibility, attributing the causes of conflict primarily to others or to external circumstances. This is often accompanied by avoidance of self-reflection and limited awareness of their own contribution to interpersonal difficulties.

At the same time, adolescents with a low level of conflictological culture demonstrate higher levels of internal conflict. This internal conflict manifests as psychological tension, inconsistency between different self-representations, and emotional instability. Such adolescents often experience difficulties integrating various aspects of their identity, which leads to heightened inner contradictions and vulnerability in stressful interpersonal situations. Their responses tend to be impulsive and emotionally driven, rather than deliberate and regulated. The data indicate that as internal conflict increases, the ability to regulate emotions and to cognitively process conflict situations decreases. Consequently, adolescents with low conflictological culture are characterized by elevated levels of internal emotional discomfort and insufficient development of self-regulation mechanisms.

Self-confidence is another important dimension of adolescent self-attitude associated with a conflict-based culture. The results show that adolescents with a high level of conflict culture are more confident in themselves and that adolescents have a sufficient level of its development. These findings suggest that subjective self-confidence is closely linked to the development of competencies relevant to conflict regulation (Mayer, 2015). While subjective self-confidence can sometimes reflect inflated self-esteem that is not grounded in actual skills, in this case, higher levels of conflictological competence are associated with higher levels of self-confidence, indicating a more realistic and functional basis for positive self-evaluation.

High self-confidence in this context is associated with effective emotional self-regulation, an adequate level of reflexivity, and cognitive maturity. It is also reflected in more confident and flexible behavioral strategies in conflict situations. Adolescents with these characteristics demonstrate a willingness to engage in dialogue, listen to alternative viewpoints, and take into account the perspectives of others. When supported by social maturity and reflective capacity, self-confidence becomes a flexible and adaptive construct. It is expressed through a balance of cooperation and self-assertion, a reduced tendency toward excessive self-criticism, sufficient sensitivity to feedback, and a clear sense of personal identity that the adolescent is prepared to defend in constructive ways. In this sense, self-confidence can be understood as an indicator of psychological and social maturity rather than mere self-enhancement.

Adolescents' attitudes toward others also vary depending on their level of conflictological culture, particularly in relation to aggressive and authoritarian

interpersonal styles. Adolescents with a low level of development of a conflict culture are increasingly choosing an aggressive type of interaction in interpersonal relationships. These findings indicate that adolescents with lower levels of conflictological culture are less capable of regulating their emotional responses in conflict situations and are less inclined to engage in cognitive analysis of interpersonal dynamics and potential consequences. As a result, they are more likely to resort to direct, forceful strategies aimed at asserting dominance or “pushing through” their own position.

Such adolescents often fail to recognize the value of dialogue, mutual understanding, and the consideration of others’ interests. Instead, they tend to perceive conflict as a competitive process centered around status, control, and power. In contrast, adolescents with a high level of conflictological culture are more likely to adopt cooperative and collaborative approaches to conflict resolution. They possess well-developed self-regulation skills, are capable of using language and communication rather than force, and are less dependent on authoritarian forms of self-assertion. For them, conflict is not primarily a confrontation but a process of negotiating and aligning different positions. Their interpersonal orientation is characterized by altruism and friendliness.

The negative association between aggression and the culture of thinking suggests that cognitive development plays a crucial role in reducing aggressive tendencies. The more capable an adolescent is of analyzing situations, considering alternative perspectives, and seeking compromise, the less likely they are to exhibit aggressive behavior (Lannin et al., 2022). Conversely, adolescents with low conflictological culture often display high emotional reactivity and a limited ability to regulate frustration. These characteristics form the core psychological mechanism underlying aggressive behavior. Importantly, aggression in this context is not typically a deliberate or strategic choice but rather a reactive response resulting from insufficient emotional stability and regulation.

In addition, adolescents with a low level of conflict culture resort to an authoritarian type of interaction with other people; they tend to a higher level of dominance, impose their point of view, maintaining tight control and relying on directive measures based on power strategies in relations with others. These tendencies reflect underdeveloped emotional reflection, limited cognitive flexibility, and insufficient mastery of constructive behavioral and communicative strategies required for effective conflict resolution.

Authoritarian tendencies in these adolescents are particularly associated with cognitive aspects of conflict processing, including stereotyped thinking, rigidity of judgments, polarized perceptions, and a reduced capacity to take the perspective of another person. The observed relationship with behavioral culture suggests a discrepancy between declared attitudes and actual behavior, which further limits their ability to engage in dialogue, mutual acceptance, cooperation, and non-violent conflict resolution (Mason, 2022). As a result, their interpersonal functioning remains constrained and less adaptive.

In summary, the findings provide strong evidence for qualitative differences in self-attitudes, attitudes toward others, levels of conflict, and conflict behavior strategies among older adolescents with different levels of conflictological culture development. Adolescents with higher levels of conflictological culture demonstrate greater emotional competence, cognitive flexibility, and behavioral adaptability, which enable them to navigate interpersonal conflicts more effectively and constructively. In contrast, lower levels of conflictological culture are associated with emotional instability, cognitive rigidity, and maladaptive behavioral patterns, which increase the likelihood of conflict escalation and reduce the effectiveness of conflict resolution.

5. Conclusion

The results of the study indicate that conflictological culture is a complex and integrative construct that plays a significant role in adolescents' psychological and social functioning. Its level is closely associated with how adolescents experience, interpret, and manage conflict situations, as well as how they relate to themselves and to others.

Adolescents with a well-developed conflictological culture demonstrate higher emotional competence, including the ability to recognize and regulate their own emotions and to understand the emotional states of others. They tend to approach conflict situations in a more constructive and reflective manner, showing the capacity for analysis, perspective-taking, and the search for mutually acceptable solutions. Their behavior is characterized by flexibility, cooperation, and a preference for dialogue over confrontation.

In contrast, adolescents with a lower level of conflictological culture are more prone to emotional instability, impulsive reactions, and internal tension. They experience greater difficulties in self-regulation and are less inclined toward reflection, which limits their ability to understand their own role in конфликт situations. As a result, they are more likely to engage in maladaptive patterns of behavior and to perceive conflict as a struggle for control or dominance.

Self-attitude also differs significantly depending on the level of conflictological culture. Adolescents with higher levels tend to demonstrate balanced self-confidence, constructive self-reflection, and a capacity to take responsibility without excessive self-blame. Their self-confidence is flexible and grounded in emotional and cognitive maturity. In contrast, lower levels are associated with avoidance of self-reflection, externalization of responsibility, and less adaptive forms of self-perception.

Differences are also evident in interpersonal relations. Lower levels of conflictological culture are associated with more aggressive and authoritarian interaction styles, characterized by rigidity, dominance, and reduced sensitivity to others' perspectives. Higher levels, on the other hand, are linked to more prosocial orientations, including cooperation, empathy, and respect for others' viewpoints.

Overall, the findings suggest that conflictological culture serves as an important developmental resource that supports emotional stability, cognitive

flexibility, and constructive interpersonal behavior. Its development contributes to more effective conflict resolution and enhances adolescents' capacity for adaptive social interaction (Chaudhary & Arora, 2023).

From a practical standpoint, these results highlight the importance of fostering conflictological culture through psychological and educational interventions aimed at developing emotional awareness, reflective thinking, communication skills, and constructive behavioral strategies.

Based on the obtained results, it is *recommended to implement educational programs* aimed at developing adolescents' conflictological culture, with a particular focus on emotional self-regulation, communication skills, and constructive conflict resolution strategies. An important direction of psychological and pedagogical work should involve teaching adolescents to recognize and understand their own emotions, as well as to develop empathy and the ability to consider another person's perspective. It would also be beneficial to integrate training activities focused on cooperation, dialogue skills, compromise seeking, and non-violent conflict resolution into the educational process.

Special attention should be paid to the development of adolescents' reflective thinking, including their ability to analyze the causes of conflicts, anticipate the consequences of their actions, and take responsibility for their behavior. The findings indicate the necessity of preventive work with adolescents who demonstrate aggressive and authoritarian interaction styles, as well as high levels of internal conflict and emotional tension. Group-based interventions aimed at fostering trust, mutual understanding, and positive social experiences may be particularly effective.

Teachers are encouraged to create an educational environment characterized by psychological safety, cooperation, and respectful communication while minimizing rigid and authoritarian interaction practices. Supporting adolescents' adequate self-esteem and self-confidence through the recognition of achievements, encouragement of independence, and involvement in socially meaningful activities is also essential. To this end, teachers in the classroom can also stimulate decentralized interaction in the classroom, encourage dialogue and equal partnerships instead of authoritarian and directive methods of self-affirmation. Teachers can provide more pedagogical support for self-esteem and self-confidence. An adult's assessment, based on the real achievements of adolescents in communication, helps to create a functional basis for the formation of self-acceptance in them.

The results further emphasize the importance of cooperation between schools and families in promoting constructive communication and conflict resolution skills. The comprehensive development of the emotional, cognitive, communicative, and behavioral components of conflictological culture may therefore be considered a significant factor in adolescents' psychological well-being and social adaptation.

In conclusion, conflictological culture can be viewed as a key factor in promoting adolescents' psychological well-being and social competence, enabling them to navigate conflicts in a more mature and adaptive way. Consequently, the development of a conflict-based culture in adolescence contributes to the formation

of emotional stability, the ability to self-regulation and constructive interaction with others. A high level of conflict management culture helps adolescents not only reduce the level of interpersonal tension, but also build more trusting, respectful and productive relationships with peers and adults. In addition, the developed skills of constructive conflict resolution become an important resource for social adaptation, personal growth and the prevention of deviant and aggressive forms of behavior.

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